

IMPACT OF COUNSELING ON MOTHER KNOWLEDGE AND CHALLENGES ABOUT THE GLUTEN FREE DIET OF CELIAC DISEASE CHILD

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Abstract

Background:

Celiac disease is a severe chronic autoimmune disorder induced by the ingestion of gluten, affects multiple systems. Strict, lifelong adherence to a gluten-free diet, which comprises avoiding wheat, rye, barley, and other gluten-containing foods, is the only treatment for celiac disease.

Aim:

The study aimed to assess the awareness, knowledge, and challenges faced by mothers of children with celiac disease regarding the implementation of a gluten-free diet, and to determine the correlation between maternal knowledge and the challenges encountered in managing the diet.

Methodology:

A correlational observational study design was conducted at one of the largest public hospitals in Lahore, Pakistan. A non-probability convenient sample of n=70 mothers of Celiac disease children were recruited from the selected hospital. Data was collected through structured self-administered validated quantitative questionnaires comprised of Demographic data, awareness and knowledge regarding gluten free diet and challenges faced by mothers in adhering to gluten free diet. Descriptive and inferential statistics, such as Pearson correlation, were used to categorize and evaluate the knowledge and challenge scores in order to investigate the relationship between challenges and knowledge levels. Prior to data collection, informed consent and ethical approval was obtained. Data was entered and interpreted through SPSS Version 23.

Results:

Findings revealed that only 24.3% of mothers had good knowledge, 67.1% faced moderate challenges and 28.6% faced high challenges while practicing gluten free diet. Moreover the findings show that knowledge and challenges have a strong and statistically significant negative correlation ($r = -0.916$ ($p < 0.01$)).

Conclusion:

Overall, the study's findings show that knowledge gaps continue to play a major role in the challenges they face. Improving mothers' knowledge is essential to lowering challenges in diet implementation

INTRODUCTION:

The global burden of disease is increasingly shifting from communicable to non-communicable diseases (NCDs). Non-communicable diseases (NCDs) are of increasing concern for society and national governments, as well as globally due to their high mortality rate (Jabeen et al., 2022). NCDs involves cardiovascular diseases, cancer, respiratory diseases, diabetes and autoimmune diseases (Odunyemi, Rahman, & Alam, 2023). In autoimmune diseases, there are many diseases, including celiac disease.

Celiac disease is a severe autoimmune disorder induced by the ingestion of gluten (Mozzillo et al., 2022). A chronic autoimmune disease that affects multiple systems, celiac disease (CD) is brought on by gluten, a protein present in intake of wheat, barley, and rye) and causes intestinal damage (Elsawah et al., 2024).

Gluten consumption causes celiac disease (CD), a chronic immune-mediated systemic illness that affects people who are genetically predisposed (Husby et al., 2020). In people who are genetically predisposed, eating gluten causes celiac disease (CD), an autoimmune entero-pathy. One of the gluten-related conditions known as CD is characterized by a small bowel enteropathy that develops in genetically predisposed people when they are exposed to the protein gliadin. Wheat, barley, and rye include gluten proteins and associated prolamins that cause autoimmune damage to the uterus, joints, skin, liver, and gut, among other organs (Elsahoryi et al., 2020a).

Globally, Celiac disease is now recognized as major health issue due to its prevalence of 1% (Kurppa et al., 2024). Approximately 1% to 3% of the population in Pakistan is diagnosed with celiac disease, however, a concerning statistic reveals that 90% of these individuals remain undiagnosed (Akhtar et al.). It is estimated that 29.3% of people in Pakistan suffer from celiac disease (Khan et al., 2022) The prevalence of

Celiac Disease reported in the Lahore region is alarmingly high. Celiac disease frequency in the pediatric population of Lahore is 17.8% and roughly one out of every 18 children among 100 has this condition (Asim, 2022).

According to recent data from histology-based screening surveys, the prevalence of undiagnosed CD in Europe varies between 0.10 and 3.03 percent and has been steadily rising year. In areas like Scandinavia, Finland, and Spain, the incidence of diagnosed CD has increased to as high as 50 per 100,000 person-years; the increases have been greater in older age groups than in newborns and early children. This emphasizes the necessity of better screening and awareness campaigns to combat underdiagnoses and the health hazards that go along with it (Roberts et al., 2021). In nations like Saudi Arabia, Jordan, Egypt, Iran, and Turkey, the combined sero-prevalence of CD is estimated to be 1.6% (Singh et al., 2018).

A strict gluten-free diet (GFD) must be followed for the rest of one's life in order to manage symptoms and avoid long-term consequences. This is the only effective treatment. Even though it affects only 1% of people worldwide, awareness and diagnosis rates are still poor; only 36% of those affected receive a diagnosis globally (Pancheva et al., 2025).

Strict, lifelong adherence to a gluten-free diet (GFD), which comprises avoiding wheat, rye, barley, and other gluten-containing foods, is the only treatment for celiac disease (CD). This results in the symptoms going away and the nutritional status improving (Ben Houmich & Admou, 2021).

The GFD continues to be the only treatment approach for gluten-related illnesses. However, since gluten is a major element in most foods, following a GFD might be difficult. Since 80% of food products contain gluten or traces of it, there is a significant chance of unintentional gluten exposure (Bilaver et al., 2021).

Maintaining a strict, lifelong gluten-free diet is essential for managing celiac disease. But the real-world challenges of sticking to this diet highlight the need for specialized management techniques. Adherence to the gluten-free diet is greatly impacted by parental knowledge of the nutritional and clinical components of celiac disease. Patients' quality of life is significantly impacted by the long-term dietary limitations imposed by the gluten-free regimen. This highlights how crucial it is to manage celiac disease holistically, taking into account not just medical aspects but also psychological and nutritional aspects in order to improve diet compliance and patients' quality of life (Ainsworth & Soon, 2023).

Avoiding dangerous grains, keeping an eye on food labels, and making sure there is no cross-contact with gluten-containing foods are all necessary to maintain a GFD. Teenagers, who frequently worry about fitting in with their classmates, want to feel normal, and may find gluten-free foods unpleasant, may find these restrictions especially difficult (Elsawah et al., 2024).

Even while the GFD helps people who are gluten intolerant, it can be difficult to follow strictly for health reasons and may affect lifestyle choices (Arias-Gastelum et al., 2018). Dietitians and nutritionists are rarely or never involved in developing balanced menus in public food services. While social and nutritional support services are still in their infancy, imported gluten-free products are only available in small numbers and at exorbitant costs. Studies at the national level that concentrate on treatments to strengthen these factors and, as a result, increase people's autonomy after a GFD are required. Raising public awareness is essential to managing nutritional therapy for people with GRD (Turcanu & Siminiuc, 2025).

The necessary information that patients should be given in order to properly follow a GFD is outlined in certain guidelines. These include describing the condition and the need for a lifelong GFD, creating a balanced GFD, talking about the advantages of following a GFD and the dangers of nutritional deficiencies, locating hidden gluten in different foods and important cross-

contamination points, teaching patients how to read labels before buying gluten-free food, offering safety advice when dining out and traveling, and making sure they have access to celiac support groups and resources (Crespo-Escobar et al., 2024).

Families may find this diet to be extremely restrictive and difficult, and many struggle with the chronic nature of both the illness and GFD (Dowhaniuk et al.).

The CD child's family is dedicated to minimizing gluten contamination in household food. The amount of gluten that might be present in the home varied from having no gluten to having shared gluten and gluten-free kitchens, to having some gluten from outside in specific locations. On the GFD, mothers were viewed as the primary educators and the ones who encountered the most challenges (Russo et al., 2020).

Patients become confused and frustrated when they unnecessarily restrict certain foods, which limits the variety and nutritional quality of their diet. Unfortunately, parents often receive outdated, inaccurate, and/or conflicting information from internet resources (depending on their response regarding the source of information). Regarding the role of food and nutrition in the prevention, treatment, and progression of acute and chronic diseases, as well as how disease and treatment impact food and nutritional demands, the qualified health care professionals—dietitians in particular—have substantial academic and practical expertise; Information about food composition preparation (Elsahoryi et al., 2020a).

Good parental knowledge of CD" and "family type" both favorably affect GFD compliance (Macedo-Campos et al., 2021). The majority of families and their CD-afflicted children are aware that a GF diet is necessary, however many lack comprehensive knowledge of the nutritional restrictions (Mager et al., 2022).

In contrast to the developed world, most developing nations like Pakistan are unaware of the financial burden of adhering to a GFD and the availability of GFD. As a result, there is little information available in these nations regarding the awareness of gluten-free dietary compliance, as

well as the knowledge and lifestyle challenges faced by people who actually benefit from a GFD. The purpose of this correlational study is to evaluate the parents' self-management, awareness, and knowledge of celiac disease and gluten-free diet. The study also aims to draw attention to the relationship between parents' knowledge of GFD and the challenges they have when trying to follow a strict gluten-free diet plan for their kids.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To evaluate the level of awareness among mothers regarding celiac disease and the importance of a gluten-free diet.
2. To assess the depth of maternal knowledge concerning gluten-containing foods and dietary management strategies.
3. To identify the common challenges mothers face in implementing and maintaining a gluten-free diet for their children.
4. To analyze the correlation between maternal awareness, knowledge, and the

challenges encountered in managing a gluten-free diet.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A correlational observational study design was conducted at one of the largest public hospital in Lahore, Pakistan. A non-probability convenient sample of n=70 mothers of Celiac disease children were recruited from the selected hospital. Sample size of 70 cases was calculated with 95% confidence interval, 5% margin of error and expected percentage of disease prevalence was 5% (Pancheva et al., 2025).

$$n = \frac{Z_{1-\alpha/2}^2 p(1-p)}{d^2}$$

Where,

1-α	95
P	0.05
d	0.05
n	70

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Sample Size for Frequency in a Population

Population size(for finite population correction factor or fpc)(N): 1000
 Hypothesized % frequency of outcome factor in the population (p): 5%+/-5
 Confidence limits as % of 100(absolute +/- %)(d): 5%
 Design effect (for cluster surveys-DEFF): 1

Sample Size(n) for Various Confidence Levels

ConfidenceLevel(%)	Sample Size
95%	69
80%	31
90%	49
97%	83
99%	113
99.9%	171
99.99%	224

Equation

Sample size $n = [DEFF * Np(1-p)] / [(d^2 / Z_{1-\alpha/2}^2 * (N-1) + p*(1-p)]$

Results from OpenEpi, Version 3, open source calculator--SSPropor
 Print from the browser with ctrl-P
 or select text to copy and paste to other programs.

Inclusion Criteria

- ▶ A confirmed diagnosis of celiac disease for the respondent or their child

- ▶ Voluntary participation.

Exclusion criteria

▶ Children with major medical conditions, who were not able to take part in study were also excluded.

▶ Mothers who have attended educational or counseling courses

First of all permission of the Institutional review board (IRB) of the Department of Nursing, the Superior University was granted. After that the Primary Investigator coordinated with the parents in order to explain them the research objectives and processes, confidentiality, risks, benefits, and participants' rights. Then their written permission was taken through written informed consent. Data for the awareness, knowledge and challenges were collected through validated knowledge and challenges based questionnaire. A self-reported awareness questionnaire was adopted from (Alhousseini et al., 2023) and was used to collect the data. This tool consisted of 8 items in total with a score of 0 to 8. Participants' knowledge was assessed through a knowledge based questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of two parts. Part A has 8 questions with one correct response each (Ayub et al., 2021), while the part B consisted of 17 questions where correct and incorrect responses was assessed (Pohoreski, Horwitz, & Gidrewicz, 2023). This tool consisted of 25 items, where the maximum knowledge score will be 25. Higher scores indicate higher levels of knowledge. Participants' challenges were assessed through a questionnaire adopted from (Arias-Gastelum et al., 2018). The questionnaire consisted of 8 questions where each question is given three options as 0= no influence, 1= moderate influence and 2= high influence. This tool has the maximum challenges score as 26. Higher scores indicate higher levels of challenges. Content Validity index (CVI) testing was done to check the content validity for the Awareness, Knowledge and Challenges tool. The CVI for awareness scale questionnaire is (0.90), CVI for

Knowledge questionnaire A is (0.925), CVI for Knowledge questionnaire part B is (0.905) and the CVI for challenges Scale questionnaire is (0.92). The Reliability of the questionnaires is checked through Cronbach's Alpha after conducting the pilot study. The pilot study was conducted on n=10 participants. The Cronbach's Alpha value for awareness measurement scale questionnaire is .736, the Cronbach's Alpha value for the knowledge questionnaire part A and B was 0.732 and .748 respectively while the Cronbach's Alpha value for challenges scale questionnaire was 0.714. Participants were recruited based on their willingness with the help of a written informed consent. The filled questionnaires were collected and processed for the data analysis.

Data was entered and analyzed by using SPSS (version 21). The knowledge, awareness and challenges were determined using frequencies and percentages. Descriptive findings were disseminated through frequency distribution tables and various graphs such as pie chart etc. The demographic data was analyzed by descriptive statistics. Regression and correlation was used to examine the relationship of awareness with the knowledge and challenges among parents regarding gluten free diet. P-value <0.05 was considered as significant.

RESULTS

This section presents the outcomes concerning the demographic traits of the study participants and their children. Moreover this chapter also presents the results about the Knowledge and challenges among mothers and the relationship of knowledge to challenges as well. The statistical methods employed encompassed the descriptive methods for the demographic characteristics, Chi square for the association of demographic factors with the knowledge and the challenges and Pearson correlation to see the relationship between the knowledge of mothers with the challenges faced by them.

Tables 1: Demographic data (n=70).

Demographic characteristics	F	(%)
Gender		
Male	41	58.6%

Female	29	41.4%
Age of the child		
3-<6 years	12	17.1%
6-9 years	41	58.6%
10-12 years	14	20%
13-15 years	3	4.3%
Age at Diagnosis		
<2 years	6	8.6%
2-4 years	44	62.9%
5-6 years	17	24.3%
>6 years	3	4.3%
Duration of disease		
<2 years	2	2.9%
2-4 years	41	58.6%
>4 years	27	38.6%
Age of Mothers		
18-24 years	7	10%
25-30 years	35	50%
31-36 years	15	21.4%
37-42 years	8	11.4%
>42 years	5	7.1%
Education of Mothers		
Uneducated	14	20%
Primary	25	35.7%
Secondary	21	30%
College and above	10	14.3%

According to the above table 1, participants' demographics, male child made up the majority of responders (58.6%), with female child making up 41.4%. The majority of children with celiac disease (58.6%) were between the ages of 6 years and 9 years of age, followed by those aged 10 to 12 years (20%) and 3 years to less than 6 years were (17.1%), with only 4.3% falling into the 13 -15 years of age range. In terms of diagnosis age, a sizable percentage (62.9%) were diagnosed between the ages of 2 and 4 years, suggesting early detection; 24.3% were diagnosed between the ages of 5 and 6 years, and fewer were diagnosed before the age of 2 years (8.6%) or after the age of 6 years

(4.3%). Just 2.9% of people had celiac disease for less than two years, whereas 58.6% had it for two to four years and 38.6% for more than four years. The age distribution of the mothers revealed that half (50%) were between the ages of 25 to 30 years, 21.4% were between the ages of 31 to 36 years, and 10% were younger (18-24 years). The percentages of mothers who were between the ages of 37 to 42 years (11.4%) and older than 42 years (7.1%) were lower. In terms of education, the majority of mothers had only primary school (35.7%), followed by secondary school (30%), while 20% were uneducated and 14.3% had college-level or higher education.

AWARENESS REGARDING CELIAC DISEASE AND GLUTEN FREE DIET

The results in above Fig.1 pertaining to participants' knowledge and information sources regarding the gluten-free diet (GFD) reveal that a significant majority (88.6%) had heard of the GFD, whereas only 11.4% said they were unaware of it.

Fig. 1 revealed that 40% of respondents correctly linked the goal of a gluten-free diet to managing an illness, but a sizable portion thought it was meant to help them lose weight (31.4%) or maintain a healthy lifestyle (18.5%), with 10% not sure.

Figure 1: LEVEL OF AGGRESSION AMONG PARTICIPANTS:

Table 2. Knowledge among Mothers Regarding Celiac Disease and Gluten Free Diet (n=70)

Knowledge Level among Mothers		
	Frequency	(%)
Poor Knowledge = Score < 50%	17	24.3%
Satisfactory Knowledge = Score 50%-72%	36	51.4%
Good Knowledge = Score >72%	17	24.3%

Findings presented in table 2, revealed that just over half of the participants (51.4%) showed satisfactory knowledge, scoring between 50% and 72% on the knowledge evaluation pertaining to mothers' knowledge of celiac disease and the gluten-free diet, according to the data. With 24.3% of mothers in each category, the percentage of mothers in the low knowledge level and good

knowledge groups was equal. This suggests that only a tiny percentage have a thorough and precise knowledge of the condition and dietary requirements, whilst the majority just have a rudimentary knowledge. On the other hand, a sizable portion of mothers continue to lack sufficient awareness, underscoring the necessity of focused educational initiatives to enhance

knowledge and care of celiac disease and gluten-free diet compliance.

Table 3. Challenges among Mothers Regarding Celiac Disease and Gluten Free Diet (n=70)

Challenges Level among Mothers	Control Group	
	Frequency	(%)
Low challenges = Score < 50%	3	4.3%
Moderate challenges = Score 50%-75%	47	67.1%
High Challenges = Score >75%	20	28.6%

According to the results of the study in table 3, on mothers' challenges with celiac disease and the gluten-free diet, most participants (67.1%) had moderate challenges, with scores ranging from 50% to 75% on the challenge evaluation scale. A smaller percentage (28.6%) expressed high levels of challenges, suggesting that controlling the illness and following dietary guidelines are extremely challenging. Just 4.3% of mothers

reported low degrees of challenges, indicating that they had little trouble handling the responsibilities of caring for their child's illness. These findings demonstrate that the majority of women encounter significant challenges in maintaining appropriate dietary management, which could be attributed to elements like restricted availability of gluten-free items, a lack of awareness, or a lack of community or healthcare system assistance.

Table 4. The Relationship between Knowledge and the Socio-demographic factors (n=70)

S. No	Demographic Variable	Status	Poor or satisfactory Knowledge f (%)	Good Knowledge f (%)	P. Value
1	Gender of Child	Male	33 (47.14%)	8 (11.42%)	.397
		Female	20 (28.57%)	9 (12.85%)	
2	Age of Child	< 9 years	45 (64.28%)	8 (11.42%)	.004*
		> 9 years	8 (11.42%)	9 (12.85%)	
3	Duration	< 4 years	43 (61.42%)	0 (0.00%)	.000*
		> 4 years	10 (14.28%)	17 (24.28%)	
4	Mothers age	30 years or less	37 (52.85%)	5 (7.14%)	.073
		> 30 years	16 (22.84%)	12 (17.14%)	
6	Mothers Education	Primary or below	39 (55.71%)	0 (0.00%)	.000*
		Secondary or Above	14 (20.00%)	17 (24.28%)	

The association between mothers' knowledge of the gluten-free diet and different socio-demographic characteristics of both themselves and their children (n = 70) is shown in Table 4. According to the data, there is no statistically significant correlation between the gender of the child and the mother's knowledge (p = 0.397). Mothers of both male (47.14%) and female (28.57%) children are more likely to have inadequate or satisfactory knowledge. The age of the kid and the mother's knowledge, however, were significantly correlated (p = 0.004), with the

majority of mothers of children under 9 years old having inadequate or enough knowledge (64.28%). In a similar way, there was a significant correlation (p = 0.000) between duration of disease and knowledge, with 61.42% of mothers whose children had been diagnosed within 4 years having inadequate or sufficient knowledge and none having good knowledge. While there was no significant correlation between the mother's age (p = 0.073), mothers 30 years of age or younger were more likely to have inadequate or satisfactory knowledge (52.85%). Notably, there was a highly

significant correlation between mothers' education and their knowledge levels ($p = 0.000$); none of the mothers in this group had good knowledge, whereas 55.71% of mothers with only a primary education or less had inadequate or satisfactory knowledge. On the other hand,

mothers who had completed secondary school or higher had a larger percentage of good knowledge. These results imply that poor knowledge of the gluten-free diet is substantially correlated with younger child age, shorter disease duration, and lower maternal education.

Table 5. The Relationship between Challenges and the Socio-demographic factors (n=70)

S. No	Demographic Variable	Status	Low or Moderate Challenges f (%)	High Challenges f (%)	P. Value
1	Gender of Child	Male	24 (34.28%)	17 (24.28%)	.070
		Female	26 (37.14%)	3 (4.28%)	
2	Age of Child	< 9 years	35 (50.00%)	18 (25.71%)	.122
		> 9 years	15 (21.42%)	2 (2.85%)	
3	Duration	< 4 years	24 (34.28%)	19 (27.14%)	.000*
		> 4 years	26 (37.14%)	1 (1.42%)	
4	Mothers age	30 years or less	24 (34.28%)	16 (22.85%)	.035
		> 30 years	26 (37.14%)	4 (5.71%)	
6	Mothers Education	Primary or below	19 (27.14%)	20 (28.57%)	.000*
		Secondary or Above	31 (44.28%)	20 (28.57%)	

Table 5. shows how different socio-demographic characteristics ($n = 70$) relate to the challenges mothers have in providing a gluten-free diet for their children with celiac disease. Although mothers of male children (34.28%) reported low or moderate challenges slightly more frequently than mothers of female children (37.14%), there was no statistically significant correlation between the child's gender and the amount of challenges ($p = 0.070$). Mothers of children under 9 years old reported more low or moderate challenges (50%) than mothers of older children, although there was no significant correlation between the child's age with mother challenges ($p = 0.122$). Mothers of children diagnosed less than 4 years ago were more likely to face high challenges (27.14%), indicating a strong statistically significant

relationship between the length of illness and the level of challenges ($p = 0.000$). The age of the mother also had a significant correlation ($p = 0.035$), with younger mothers (those under 30 years old) reporting more challenges (22.85%) than older mothers. Notably, there was a significantly significant correlation between challenges and mother education ($p = 0.000$). While mothers with secondary education or above were more likely to report lower levels of challenges (44.28%), mothers with only primary school or less had the largest proportion of challenges (28.57%). These findings imply that greater challenges in adhering to a gluten-free diet are substantially correlated with shorter disease duration, younger mother age, and lower educational attainment.

Table 6. Correlation between Knowledge and Challenges faced by Mothers (n=70)

		Knowledge	Challenges
Knowledge	Pearson Correlation	1	-.916**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	70	.000
	N		70
Challenge	Pearson Correlation	-.916**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	70	.000
	N		70

The Pearson correlation study between mothers' knowledge of the gluten-free diet and the challenges they encounter in adhering to it is shown in Table 4.6. The findings show that knowledge and challenges have a strong and statistically significant negative correlation ($r = -0.916$, $p = 0.000$). This suggests that the challenges mothers have tend to diminish considerably as their level of knowledge rises. Better-informed mothers are likely to face less challenges in implementing and maintaining a gluten-free diet for their kid with celiac disease, as indicated by the correlation's negative direction, which shows an inverse link. This correlation is very significant and not the result of chance, as confirmed by the significance level ($p < 0.01$). This research highlights how important awareness and education are in lowering the practical challenges faced by mothers of children with celiac disease.

DISCUSSION

In this current study, majority 75% of the participants with breast cancer were 46 years and above

Findings of the current study revealed that only 11.4% of participants in the current study were not aware of the gluten-free diet (GFD), compared to a significant majority (88.6%) who said they had heard of it. In contrast to earlier research, this suggests a rather high level of awareness. For instance, compared to the results of the current study, 76% of the participants in (Alhusseini et al., 2023) had prior awareness of the GFD. A far lower level of awareness than that found in the current study was found by (Taşkin & Savlak, 2020), who evaluated people's knowledge of celiac disease itself and found that 50.9% had heard of it, 43.9% had never heard of it, and the remaining people were unclear. Increased public health campaigns, more access to health information on social media, and better doctor-patient interactions in recent years may all be responsible for the higher awareness in the current study. Although awareness alone does not always result in precise information or adherence without focused education, this points to a good trend toward increased public acknowledgment of dietary management measures for celiac disease.

According to the current study, the most common sources of information about the gluten-free diet were the internet and social media (47.1%), followed by celiac patient associations (24.3%), doctors (5.7%), dietitians or nutritionists (15.7%), and other sources (7.1%). These results demonstrate how peer networks and digital platforms dominate the dissemination of nutritional information. By contrast, a past research found that parents mostly sourced their knowledge from the internet/social media (40%) or a gastroenterology clinic (40%) and that dietitians contributed the least amount (20%) (Elsahoryi et al., 2020a). The current findings show a comparatively lesser reliance on healthcare professionals, especially physicians, as primary information sources, even if both research highlight the important importance of internet resources. This can be the result of shorter consultation times during clinical visits, simpler access to online resources, or potential deficiencies in the proactive dietary advice given by medical professionals. These findings highlight the need for healthcare professionals, particularly dietitians and doctors, to play a more active role in providing trustworthy, evidence-based advice on gluten-free diets, especially as information from social media may differ in accuracy.

In the current study 42.9% of participants correctly identified gluten as a protein present in barley, rye, and wheat. Participants' modest knowledge of the fundamental idea of gluten is reflected in this level of knowledge. In contrast, the majority of participants in a Saudi Arabian study by (Alhusseini et al., 2023) correctly identified gluten as a protein present in certain grains, indicating a higher level of awareness. Furthermore, they discovered that over half (58%) of participants were aware of both gluten and the gluten-free diet (GFD), indicating a higher level of public familiarity. The current study's low percentage of accurate answers could be the result of differences in educational attainment, access to health information, or exposure to dietary advice. Given that correct knowledge is necessary for appropriate adherence to a gluten-free diet in managing celiac disease, these findings highlight the need for further educational initiatives to

improve basic awareness of gluten. To empower patients and caregivers alike, health professionals and community awareness initiatives should concentrate on elucidating such fundamental ideas.

In the present study 40% of participants accurately recognized the main objective of a gluten-free diet (GFD) as treating an illness, although a significant percentage thought it was meant to help them lose weight (31.4%) or maintain a healthy lifestyle (18.5%), and 10% were not sure. Similar to this, the majority of participants acknowledged "disease management" as the primary goal of a GFD, followed by "healthy lifestyle," according to (Alhousseini et al., 2023), suggesting a similar pattern of ambiguous knowledge. Social media narratives that support gluten-free eating as a general health or weight-control approach, celebrity endorsements, and popular media trends may all contribute to the longevity of non-medical beliefs, such as the association of GFD with weight loss. People with celiac disease may not completely understand the medical necessity of stringent dietary compliance as a result of such misconceptions, which could compromise adherence. These findings highlight the value of focused education in separating the therapeutic intent of a GFD from widely held but unsupported assumptions.

A little over half of the participants in this study (51.4%) scored between 50% and 72%, indicating satisfactory knowledge of the gluten-free diet (GFD), while the same percentage (24.3%) fell into the low-knowledge and good-knowledge groups. These results imply that although a sizable percentage of mothers have sufficient information, there is still a significant knowledge gap at both extremes. In contrast, (Elsahoryi et al., 2020b) found that 86% of parents had average knowledge scores, 8% had bad knowledge scores, and just 6% had good knowledge scores. This suggests that there is more focus in the middle range and fewer with high knowledge levels than in the current study. (Elsawah et al., 2024), on the other hand, discovered that mothers of children with celiac disease tended to have low knowledge (65.1%), with just 19.4% having fair knowledge and 15.5% having strong knowledge. This

indicates that there are significant disparities in the distribution of knowledge between samples. Similar critical gaps have been found in other recent studies: (Tsurcanu & Siminiuc, 2025) reported that while 77.3% of participants could correctly define gluten, only 16.1% scored above 50% on identifying gluten-containing foods, while (Pancheva et al., 2025) found that only 16.6% of participants were aware of the prevalence of celiac disease. Additionally, (Soin, 2025) observed that whereas 57.4% of respondents said they had a general awareness of celiac disease, just 18.5% said they knew more than average, and 24% were unsure or uninformed. Together, these trends show that diverse communities still lack precise and thorough knowledge regarding celiac disease and GFD, despite differing levels of awareness. In contrast to some previous studies, the current study's reasonably balanced distribution of satisfactory and low/good knowledge categories indicates progress in public knowledge. However, it also emphasizes the ongoing need for focused educational interventions to close important knowledge gaps, especially in identifying gluten sources, comprehending the prevalence of the disease, and realizing the medical necessity of strict dietary adherence.

With scores ranging from 50% to 75% on the challenges evaluation scale, the majority of participants (67.1%) in this study reported moderate challenges following a gluten-free diet (GFD), whereas 28.6% reported significant challenges. These results suggest that treating the disease and adhering to dietary recommendations continue to be significant challenges for many mothers. These challenges could result from a lack of knowledge, insufficient assistance from the community or healthcare system, and restricted access to and price of gluten-free items.

Previous studies have emphasized similar challenges. For instance, 83.6% of participants brought their own food when dining outside, a practice that reflects both caution and a lack of confidence in the options available. (Pancheva et al., 2025) found that societal challenges and misconceptions about gluten-containing food significantly hindered dietary adherence. Additionally, with 10.4% having very low food

security and 23.2% experiencing GFD insecurity, (Smeets, Kieft-de Jong, & van der Velde, 2024) also found a high correlation between perceived impediments to GFD adherence and food insecurity. Participants with poor and very low food security were much more likely to experience challenges with social circumstances, cooking abilities, resource availability, and the availability of naturally gluten-free items. The fact that these results are consistent with the current study emphasizes that dietary management issues are influenced by larger structural and socioeconomic factors in addition to personal knowledge and motivation. Comprehensive interventions will be needed to address these challenges, such as increased product availability, focused nutritional education, and legislative actions to lower costs and improve food security for families with celiac disease.

In the current study, there was no statistically significant association between the mother's knowledge of the gluten-free diet (GFD) and the child's gender ($p = 0.397$). This suggests that mothers of both male (47.14%) and female (28.57%) children were more likely to have knowledge that was either insufficient or satisfactory. However, the majority of mothers with children under 9 years old (64.28%) had inadequate or satisfactory knowledge, and there was a significant correlation between maternal knowledge and child age ($p = 0.004$). This research raises the possibility that early phases of disease management could be marked by a lack of knowledge, perhaps as a result of a shorter learning curve and less opportunities for dietary guidance.

Mothers whose children had been diagnosed during the last four years (61.42%) tended to have inadequate or satisfactory knowledge, and none showed good knowledge. Similarly, a highly significant connection ($p = 0.000$) was identified between the length of the disease and maternal knowledge.

Mothers 30 years or younger were more likely to fall into the inadequate or satisfactory category (52.85%), which may be connected to a lack of experience providing care or a lack of exposure to health education. However, there was no

significant correlation between maternal age and knowledge ($p = 0.073$). The strongest result was that mother knowledge and education were significantly correlated ($p = 0.000$).

This relationship pattern is consistent with other earlier research. Similar findings were made by (Taşkin & Savlak, 2020), who found that the only demographic factor significantly correlated with knowledge was education level ($p < 0.05$). The most knowledgeable participants (79.6% of postgraduates) were the most educated, while the least knowledgeable participants ($p = 0.000$) were the least educated. (Elsawah et al., 2024) also discovered a significantly significant correlation ($p < 0.01$) between knowledge and the age of the child and the educational attainment of both parents. Moreover, according to (Tsurcanu & Siminiuc, 2025), the greatest knowledge scores were associated with higher academic accomplishment, especially at the master's degree level. This tendency was further reinforced by (Eida, 2022), which found a strong correlation with education level ($p < 0.05$) but no significant differences in knowledge by age, residence, income, or family characteristics. All of these results point to the importance of mothers' education in influencing the level of knowledge regarding celiac disease and GFD adherence. Increased educational attainment may improve the ability to critically evaluate nutritional misunderstandings, make it easier to acquire trustworthy information sources, and improve knowledge of dietary requirements. On the other hand, people with less education might find it more difficult to understand complicated dietary restrictions, which could lead to ongoing knowledge gaps. In order to close these knowledge gaps quickly and enhance long-term disease management outcomes, early, intensive education at diagnosis that is customized to caregivers' educational backgrounds is crucial, as evidenced by the associations with younger child age and shorter disease duration found in this study.

According to this current study, Mothers of children with celiac disease diagnosed less than four years ago were more likely to experience high levels of challenges (27.14%) in the current study, and there was a strong statistically significant

correlation between perceived challenges and the length of the disease ($p = 0.000$). This implies that families are still getting used to the rigorous needs of a gluten-free diet (GFD) in the early years after diagnosis, and they may have more trouble finding suitable foods, deciphering product labels, and navigating dietary restrictions in social situations. Additionally, there was a significant link ($p = 0.035$) between maternal age and challenges, with younger mothers (less than 30 years old) reporting higher challenges (22.85%). This could be due to a lack of experience providing care, a lack of coping mechanisms, or a lack of access to support systems. Another important predictor was education level ($p = 0.000$); women with at least a secondary education were more likely to report less challenges (44.28%), while mothers with only a primary education or less experienced the most challenges (28.57%). This is consistent with the knowledge that a greater level of education makes it easier to grasp dietary requirements, navigate resources more effectively, and develop problem-solving abilities for handling dietary constraints. These results are in line with earlier studies. According to (Kori et al., 2021), one of the most frequent reasons why younger children and adolescents do not follow the GFD is "challenges administration." These challenges include challenges reading labels, buying gluten-free products, and dining out; these challenges are probably more severe in families with less education or a shorter history of the disease. Even after adjusting for disease duration, (Monzani et al., 2023) showed that dietary management challenges and individual factors, as assessed by the modified Leffler questionnaire, decreased the likelihood of optimal adherence by 51%. Crucially, their results also showed that adherence likelihood rose by 22% when educated by a qualified dietitian during follow-up, highlighting the need of expert nutritional counseling in overcoming challenges. When combined, the recent and earlier research shows that GFD adherence issues are complex and influenced by a number of factors, including the length of the illness, the age of the caregiver, and educational attainment. For families in the early post-diagnosis phase or with lower educational attainment, early,

structured nutrition education—ideally provided by qualified dietitians—and continued support could be crucial in lowering these challenges. Such therapies have the potential to improve children's and their caregivers' quality of life in addition to adherence.

Maternal knowledge and challenges following a gluten-free diet (GFD) for children with celiac disease were found to be strongly and statistically significantly correlated negatively in the current study ($r = -0.916$, $p = 0.000$). This research suggests that mothers' challenges implementing and sticking to the diet significantly diminish as their knowledge of celiac disease and GFD grows. The inverse association implies that knowledgeable caretakers are better able to get beyond challenges to dietary adherence that are connected to resources, social interactions, and practical considerations.

This supports the findings of (Smeets, Kieftede Jong, & van der Velde, 2024), who discovered a strong correlation between food insecurity and perceived barriers to GFD adherence. Participants who experienced low or very low food security were significantly more likely to report challenges with social situations, cooking abilities, resource availability, and access to naturally gluten-free foods. These findings demonstrate that adherence is not just determined by knowledge; social support, food availability, and affordability are important external challenges. (Vázquez-Polo et al., 2023), who found that the great majority of respondents thought that raising public awareness regarding celiac disease in the general community would improve their quality of life, further supports the significance of expanding illness-related knowledge. This emphasizes the importance of raising knowledge among family members, acquaintances, and food service providers—all of whom have a direct impact on daily dietary management—in addition to patients and their immediate caregivers. Similar to this, (Wieser et al., 2021) highlighted how a variety of factors interact with individual knowledge levels to either limit or improve adherence, including the availability, affordability, and quality of gluten-free foods, the hazards of gluten cross-contamination, and analytical challenges in gluten detection.

When combined, the recent and historical data suggest a multifaceted framework where knowledge plays a significant but not exclusive role in lowering GFD challenges. To increase the quality, cost, and accessibility of gluten-free items while also creating supportive social situations, effective interventions should integrate systemic changes with focused caregiver education. The cognitive and structural challenges that prevent effective dietary adherence in the management of celiac disease can be addressed by this integrated approach.

CONCLUSION

Overall, the study's findings show that although mothers of children with celiac disease are largely aware of the need for a gluten-free diet, knowledge gaps continue to play a major role in the challenges they face. Improving mothers' knowledge is essential to lowering challenges in diet implementation, as evidenced by the obvious and significant inverse relationship between knowledge and challenges. It is feasible to empower women, enhance dietary adherence, and eventually advance improved health outcomes and quality of life for impacted children by giving priority to focused education, culturally relevant resources, and ongoing professional assistance. Furthermore, the results highlight how important it is to empower mothers through focused awareness campaigns, helpful advice, and continuous professional support. Enhancing their knowledge of the gluten-free dietary needs can significantly reduce the challenges they encounter, improving adherence and improving the quality of life and health outcomes for kids with celiac disease.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study findings, the following recommendations can be made:

1. Implement targeted educational programs to improve mothers' knowledge of gluten-free dietary requirements and management strategies for children with celiac disease.
2. Develop culturally appropriate and easy-to-understand resources (booklets, videos, workshops) to support consistent diet adherence.

3. Provide regular professional counseling by dietitians or trained healthcare providers to address mothers' concerns and reduce challenges.
4. Establish peer support groups to enable experience sharing, emotional support, and practical tips among mothers.
5. Integrate celiac disease education into community health initiatives to increase awareness and early identification of dietary needs.

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